

ANALYSIS OF NAVOI'S ELEGY TO HIS MENTOR

Rayhonoy Goyibboyeva Ahmadjonovna,
NamSU, teacher of the Faculty of Philology
E-mail: rgoyibboyeva@gmail.com

Teshaboyeva Sevinch Islamjon qizi,
A student of the Faculty of Philology of
NamSU

Annotation. This article analyzes Alisher Navoi's elegy dedicated to the death of his teacher Abdurrahman Jami and the artistic arts used in it.

Key words: Navoi, ustoz, shams-ul-millat, arifi moni, gavhari koni, artistic arts, metaphor, diagnosis, exaggeration, talmeh, takrir, nido, irsoli masal, takrir, tanosub, tardi aks.

Our so-called strange land of Uzbekistan has been a land of scholars and great people since ancient times. Our ancestors who grew up in our motherland were experts in many fields. Whether you call it disaster or mathematics, they have achieved many achievements in all of these.

Many scientific researches have been carried out on the great priceless treasure of the great poet and thinker Mir Alisher Navoi. Nevertheless, the scientific researches and analyzes carried out to date are just a drop in the ocean.

The role of the teacher in Navoi's life and work is incomparable. The poet traditionally began the introduction of most of his works with praise to God, blessings to the prophets, and then praises to his teachers. In particular, Abdurrahman Jami occupies a special place among Navoi's teachers. The friendship between Jami and Navoi and the teacher-student relationship are of great importance. As proof of this, it is worth noting that Navoi describes his teachers Nizami and Dehlavi in one chapter. Abdurrahman devotes a whole chapter to Jami. He gives Jami high praises such as "Qutbi tariqati", "Fano symbol", "jahoni begaron" (infinite world), "alami kubro", "nurun-alo-nur", "fazl komi-yu ilm dariya" to Jami.

Abdurahman Jami died in November 1492 at the age of 78. The death of such a great and great person was the most difficult parting and a huge loss for Navoi. Along with a patriotic man like Jami, his irrevocable thinking, deep thoughts, intelligence were also buried. Losing both his mentor and his beloved friend turned Navoi's morning into night. According to the poet, the people of Khurasan and Herat mourn Jami throughout the year.

After Alisher Navoi Jami's death, he wrote the work "Khamsat ul-mutahayirin" dedicated to him. This work was completed in 1494. "Khamsat ul-mutahayirin" is translated as "Amazing Five". The work consists of 5 parts, consisting of an introduction, three articles and a conclusion. At the end of the work "Khamsat ul-mutahayirin" the full text of Navoi's elegy dedicated to his teacher in Persian is given.

The means of artistic image, expressiveness and happiness in literature are called artistic arts. The science that studies such sciences is called "Ilmi bade". Tashbeh, tashxis, mubolag'a, ruju, talmeh, takrir, nido, irsoli masal, takrir, tanosub, tardi aks, husni ta'lil, tasbe, istiora, tajohul-u orif and many similar poetic works. We can see the most beautiful examples of poetic arts in the works of Alisher Navoi.

The Marsia begins with the following lines:

Har dam az anjumani charx jafoye digar ast,

Har yak anjumi dog'i baloye digar ast.

Meaning: Every time a new threat comes from the heavenly assembly,

Each of its stars is a spot of a new calamity.

The poet begins his march with a beautiful metaphor. Every single star in the sky is called a speck of evil. Hundreds of stars are burning one by one in the dark sky, it is like a stain left from sufferings and troubles.

Proportion is created by using words that are close to each other in terms of meaning in the verse, in general, in poetic clauses. .

Guli in bog' ki sadpora zi motamzadagist,

Har yake suxtai joma-qaboi digar ast.

Meaning: The flower of this garden has faded from mourning.

Each one's clothes are burnt, the other's hair

In this verse, Navoi clearly expressed his opinion through beautiful adjectives. By garden, the poet meant this mortal world. In this garden, there were a hundred flowers from the many lamentations and mournings. We all know that a flower is a bud at first, and then it becomes big and fully opens. And when the flower is fully opened, its leaves are layered. Sorrows and mourning are so strong that the flower is broken. The poet compares the full opening of a flower to a person whose heart is broken into a hundred pieces by grief. The second stanza shows that these mournings did not fall on the head of only one person and did not bring sorrow to his heart. As a result of this mourning, this separation, other people's clothes were burnt, others' clothes were burnt. Aza-yu gards brought darkness to everyone's heart.

Diagnosis is "personalization". The prefix "ta" is derived from the Arabic root "person". It is the art of transferring the physical and mental conditions unique to humans to natural scenes, creatures, objects and concepts in life.

To'tiyoni harami quds ba dil mushtoqam,

Bulbuloni chamani uns ba jon shaydoyat

Meaning: The parrots of the harem of purity are longing for you from the heart,

The nightingales of friendship will sing to you from the soul.

Or let's look at another stanza:

Dast bar dast rabudand turo to joe

Ki, dar in g'amkada ham xosti onro royat.

Meaning: They took you hand in hand to a place where

You wanted that place even in this place of grief.

Through this verse, the poet admits that Jami's heart is adorned with the love of God and the desire to reach Him. In the second stanza, he calls this transitory world a place of sorrow. They, that is, the great spirits of the higher ranks, the saints, lifted you in their arms and took you to such a place that you would want this place even in the place of sorrow (in this world).

Dar biyoboni tamannosh xaloyiq murdand,

Ba davoi hama on Xizri Masihodam ku?

Meaning: People died in the wilderness of Orzu.

Where is Christ, the cure for all?

People's dream of seeing Jami once again was destroyed. He asks where is Jesus Christ, who is the cure for all. Christ Khizr was the one who gave life to the dead. That's why Navoi Masiha asks where is the breathless Khizr. Through this, the art of talmeh was created in this verse.

In the art of talmeh (Arabic - to glance, cast a glance), "the poet compares and compares the character of the hero with the famous literary, religious or historical heroes of the past; Sometimes the names of the heroes of the past are not mentioned, but the events related to them can be remembered. In both cases, the art of talmeh occurs.

Garchi shomi tu shud az nu chu mahtob safed,

Hech kas lek nadidast chunon ro'zu siyoh.

Meaning: Although your tone is as white as the moon with light,

But no one has seen such a dark night.

The night of the poet's death is even bright with rays, white as day. But no one, no soul has seen such a dark night. That is, no matter how much the lights illuminated the night for Jami, no one had ever seen such a severe separation, separation (black night).

In the art of Tazad (Arabic - opposition, opposite), the poet uses opposite, contradictory words in his poem. On the surface, contrast is similar to antithesis—both of them deal with opposite concepts, and at the same time, they have different aspects. Whereas in antithesis the conflicting opposites come from two independent sources, the conflicting opposites in antithesis have a single origin: one thing contains the origin of both good and evil. In the above verse, the words white and black have created the art of contrast.

Hama pokoni jahonro ba tani pok rasid,

Onchi omad ba tani pok zi aflok turo.

Meaning: You were the leader of the pure ones of the world, therefore (too) pure God,

He made you pure and took you away pure.

In this verse, Navoi describes his teacher as the leader of the world's pure ones. You were the leader of the pure in the whole world, there was no purer than you. That is why the pure God made you pure. He created you pure and took you to his deathbed.

The art of Takrir (Arabic - repetition) is the repetition of one or another word in a certain poem. The purpose of repeating a word is to emphasize the meaning and essence of that word, to draw the reader's attention to it. In this verse, the art of repetition was created by using the word pure again and again.

Shohi ma'niro gar surat aftod chunun,

Bod to hashr shah suratu ma'ni omin!

Meaning: The image of the king of meaning, if so,

Let the image be the king of the meaning!

Amen!

Navoi ends the last stanza with a confession. If this is the meaning of giving a person the gift of life and taking it away again when the time comes, then the meaning is king with the image until the destiny.

To sum up, Alisher Navoi showed himself as an incomparable, extraordinary creative potential, a great thinker, a unique poet by bringing Uzbek artistic thinking to the level of world artistic thinking. With this, the poet took the highest place among the great representatives of world literature.

Alisher Navoi enriched the range of genres and themes of Uzbek poetry with his work "Khazayin-ul Maoniy". No artist in Uzbek poetry could rise to the level of creating such a perfect divan. This poem of the poet has been repeatedly copied and published many times in several countries in full and abridged manuscripts.

The abundance of artistic arts in the poet's poetry, their appropriate use, and the fact that they are not similar to others have further increased the value of his works. He used many beautiful poetic arts with great skill in this single march. As a result, the work occupies a deeper place in the reader's heart with its charm and colorfulness. Through the many and appropriate use of poetic arts, the reader understands more deeply what the poet wants to say in his work. That is why Hazrat Navoi's priceless works have not lost their value for several years. One of the main reasons for this is probably the importance of poetic arts in the poet's lyrics.

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